

D5.2 - EPIC-WE Games Collection

Project Number: GA 101095058

Project Acronym: EPIC-WE

Project Title: Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments: Youth Imagining, Creating and Exchanging Cultural Values and Heritage Through Game-making

EPIC-WE
Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Technical References

Deliverable title	D5.2 EPIC-WE Games Collection
Document type	Demonstrator
Dissemination level	PU
Work package	WP5
Task	Task 5.3
Lead beneficiary(ies)	MEET
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Due date of deliverable	31st of January 2026
Actual submission date	15th of March 2026
Reviewed by	Regitze Mai Møller (AAKS), Nelio Codes (BS), Rikke Toft Nørgård (AU), Michelle Kok (DM), Lucrezia Paris (MEET)

Document History

Version	Date	Status
V1	15.02.2026	First full draft
V2	11.03.2026	Final revised version following review by Executive Board and Coordinator
V3	15.03.2026	Submitted final version

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EPIC-WE
Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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INTRODUCTION

Welcome to the EPIC-WE Games Collection. This D5.2 Demonstrator contains all of the Cultural Game Prototypes developed within the EPIC-WE Horizon Europe project - The project has invited more than 400 young people to create 117 cultural game prototypes during the project's 12 cultural game jams. Showcasing the potential of cultural game prototypes, you also find in the EPIC-WE Games Collection a section that features the 8 games with culture that was further matured from the cultural game prototypes by professional game companies within the project.

We are truly impressed by the sheer scale of youth's cultural imagination and engagement, but even more so with their creativity in making games through and for culture, their cultural imagination and innovative game-making processes - and the empowerment that emerged by forming an 'epic we' with youth on the potential of games through, for, and with culture. We hope you will feel the same, reading through the EPIC-We Games Collection.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

THE EPIC-WE PROJECT

EPIC-WE is an acronym for ‘Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments’

A Horizon Europe project focusing on youth imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making.

The heart of the project

At its heart, EPIC-WE shows that games are not only entertainment and cultural heritage is not stagnant or dead – when cultural worlds and experiences are brought to life through young people’s imagination, game-making, and cross-sector collaboration both culture and games benefits and become engaging and empowering in new ways.

Game-making as culture-making

EPIC-WE develops, tests, evaluates and delivers a Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model that brings Higher Education, Cultural Heritage, Creative Industries and Youth (15–25) together as equal partners in culture and games. The model comes to life through Cultural Game Jams - intensive, structured game-making events facilitated by the Cultural Hub partners and where young people co-create and transform heritage, narratives, and values into games through and for culture. Creating and showcasing their games, young people are invited to redefine cultural identity, values, engagement, and experiences and show how games can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture.

More than a project

EPIC-WE has not just been a project; it has been a journey empowering young people to shape European culture and futures in games, reframing games as cultural artefacts and game-making as civic participation; it operationalises participatory and co-creative cross-sector collaboration and delivers transferable and open available models, methods, tools, and resources. With the creation of ‘games through culture’ and ‘games for culture,’ games become culture themselves, vehicles for youths’ empowered participation in culture, and carrying the potential to engage new voices and include new identities in shaping European futures in games and culture.

What the project does

The EPIC-WE project is transforming how European culture is created, shared and preserved across Europe and beyond.

1. Unleashing the next generation of culture-makers transforming them from audiences to engaged game-makers.
2. Cultural Game Jams as immersive living laboratories for games and culture using Cultural Game Jam Kits for participatory heritage game creation.
3. Meeting in the middle in QH Cultural Hubs and cross-sector partnerships that break sectoral silos and spark cross-sector collaboration and innovation.
4. Turning culture into playable worlds and experiences that reimagine collections, archives, sites, and artifacts as game-making material.
5. Empowering participation by giving youth the steering wheel in cultural innovation positioning them as fundamental actors in the cultural innovation ecosystem

EPIC-WE shows cross-sector collaboration around game-making as culture-making can generate games and models for engaging heritage; its Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams equip young people with cultural-creative competencies, renew institutional practices in games and culture, and – when partners meet each other in the middle to form an epic we - turn culture into a playground where innovation, heritage and imagination empower each other and youth actively transform, co-shape and give voice to the cultural heritage narratives, values and identities we are all part of.

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WHAT IS A CULTURAL GAME JAM?

Cultural Game Jams aim to foster empowered cultural participation, collaboration, and a sense of belonging in culture by engaging young people in game-making as a form of culture-making.

Step inside the Cultural Game Jam: Where games meet culture

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) empower young people (ages 15–25) as co-creators of culture through game-making processes as a form of culture-making. They blend traditional game jams with cultural imagination and reflection on heritage sites, archives, artifacts, themes, and values. CGJs position games as a key form of culture-making, inviting participants to reimagine, remix, and reconfigure cultural sites, artifacts, and narratives.

The core elements: A Cultural Game Jam Kit for cultural transformation

In EPIC-WE, participants created over 100 Cultural Game Prototypes, all published on the EPIC-WE Resource Site. Using the CGJ framework and CGJ Kit, these prototypes were refined through the project's 12 CGJs. Some of these Games through/for Culture are showcased in the EPIC-WE Games EXPO Catalogue.

The CGJ framework has four phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, Create (EPIC) and focuses on cultural Worlds and Empowerment (WE). CGJ Kit's methods, tools, team roles, EU value cards, and facilitation guides structure the journey. Specialized methods for engaging culture, games, and values, along with transition tools (Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, Game Logs),

help teams refine ideas, practice cultural imagination, and integrate feedback as they move toward prototyping and creating their Games through/for Culture.

Through the CGJ framework, participants explore cultural heritage for inspiration, shape ideas through sketches and mock-ups, then prototype and playtest. Each CGJ concludes with the participants showcasing their Games through/for Culture to audiences at an EPIC-WE Games EXPO.

Cultural Game Jams: Transforming audiences into culture-makers and game-makers

CGJs provide deep, multidimensional value across sectors. In culture, they transform audiences into engaged co-creators, strengthening heritage and values and highlighting games as cultural form of expression.

Access the
Resource Site

In education and youth empowerment, CGJs act as real-world living labs, developing vital skills (collaborative, cultural, creative, technical) and fostering cultural agency, voice, and belonging. The format cultivates an “epic we” – a collective, non-hierarchical space where different participants from different sectors and disciplines collaborate across heritage, culture, and games. In this space, youth express cultural viewpoints and identities and show agency in reimagining culture and games.

The EPIC-WE project results show that Cultural Game Jams hold significant promise at the intersection of cultural heritage and game-making. Key potentials include:

Bridging culture & games: CGJs break down the dichotomy between “culture” and “games,” promoting recognition that games are cultural artifacts in themselves and that cultural game-making fosters meaning, identity, and heritage. This encourages youth to see game-making not merely as entertainment but as part of cultural and societal imagination and participation.

Heritage engagement reinterpreted: Cultural institutions often struggle to engage youth. Cultural Game Jams turn tangible and intangible heritage into game-making material for creative reimagining, rather than static artifacts. Youth remix, narrate, critique, and extend heritage creatively, producing new narratives as Games through/for Culture that connect past, present, and future.

Institutional and industry innovation:

Cultural Game Jams serve as innovation spaces for cultural institutions and creative industries. They act as cross-sector hubs and labs for participatory, co-creative approaches to culture and game-making, enabling organisations to work together and to explore new formats and methods. They also act as experimental sites, supporting talent development, fostering experimentation with value-sensitive, heritage-based game worlds, and opening pathways for culturally and socially engaged game-making. These efforts strengthen institutional and industry innovation, expand educational and industry pipelines, and cultivate a new generation of game-makers shaping culture through games.

Cultural Game Jams are not niche experiments but proven, versatile methods for transforming heritage, education, and creative industries into active, co-creative ecosystems. They reshape relationships from passive consumption to partnership, remaking culture with youth rather than just presenting it. Anyone interested in meaningful participation, future-facing cultural practice, or imaginative learning are invited to adopt Cultural Game Jams. Doing so helps organisations find new ways to interpret the past and cultivate the creative capabilities that will define our cultural futures.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

GAMES THROUGH CULTURE

Games through culture treat cultural heritage and cultural artifacts as primary game-making material and inspiration. They often integrate tangible cultural heritage more or less directly (e.g. a 'Hammershøj horror game' or a game that directly draw on selected artworks or art installations like 'My Filtered Life' using the Rainbow installation at the ARoS Art Museum). They foreground tangible cultural heritage as playable resources, transforming museum objects, nature, archives, buildings, or other cultural artefacts or sites into interactive systems that reinterpret, remix, and materialize culture as new aesthetic and experiential forms.

- **Source material role:** Cultural heritage, artifacts, places, and other sites/artifacts are used as core game-making material rather than background decoration.

- **Aesthetic remediation:** Design emphasizes reimagining, preserving, and artistically re-presenting cultural heritage through mechanics, gameworlds, aesthetics, design.
- **Site-centered making:** Development often takes place within or with specific cultural heritage sites and institutions, enabling direct access to collections and expertise that the groups' game jam with.
- **Interactive reinterpretation:** Games invite players to experience, manipulate, and extend tangible cultural heritage.
- **Local and material specificity:** Strong attachment to place, objects, and particular cultural collections and traditions produces games that are often locally rooted and materially specific.
- **Heritage-focused outcomes:** Games through culture are measured by how the game makes heritage engaging, felt, or newly meaningful to players.

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GAMES FOR CULTURE

Games for culture use game-making as a deliberate practice to explore, critique, and shape cultural values, social norms, identities, and civic imaginaries. They prioritize societal transformation, cultural dialogue, and empowerment, inviting players and creators to reflect on belonging, citizenship, and collective futures.

- **Value-driven goals:** Design is explicitly oriented toward cultural, social, or civic aims such as inclusion, identity work, or critical reflection using - in meaningful ways - the EU values.
- **Societal engagement:** Games open spaces for cultural-societal debate, empathy-building, and imagining alternative social arrangements.

- **Narrative and ethical focus:** Mechanics and stories are crafted to surface dilemmas, contested histories, and cultural narratives - highlighting EU values as a driver for change, dialogue and ethics.
- **Youth and civic empowerment:** Games for culture often aim to give underrepresented groups agency and voice in cultural-societal conversations.
- **Dialogic outcomes:** Success is evaluated by the game's ability to provoke discussion, change perspectives, or support community action.

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Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

FEATURED GAMES

Aarhus

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

In Aarhus Cultural Hub, the maturation of the selected games, Metamorphosis and 404 Fairness not found – the psykiosk game, followed a structured and value-driven process, combining youth engagement with professional expertise. Both titles were chosen after a collective evaluation and in-depth discussion of candidate projects, where all Aarhus Cultural Hub members prepared notes and assessments in advance.

The development of each game began with a joint start-up meeting involving industry partner Filmby Aarhus, the professional game studio Mothworks, and the participants from the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam, who made the two prototypes. These meetings created a shared framework of expectations, values, and artistic ambitions. The studio then presented detailed development proposals with clear artistic and technical steps.

Throughout the process, emphasis was placed on linking art and gameplay, ensuring that both games reflect EPIC-WE's ambition to bridge cultural and creative disciplines. This co-creation approach allowed young participants to contribute directly alongside professional developers.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

MOTHWORKS is an independent game studio, creating unique and striking interactive experiences.

Driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition, Mothworks is gonna blow your philosophical, artsy socks off!

They got several projects in the (moth) works.

Team behind Metamorphosis

Hello, we're Puzlerne, the creators behind the core idea of Metamorphosis; the game you now see exhibited at Aros or Filmby Aarhus.

On our team we have a programmer, a storywriter, an artist and a designer, and together we strive to create games that bring people together, give new perspectives and take the world by storm!

Team behind PsyKiosk

We are 404 Fairness Not Found, a group of students at Aarhus University, united by EPIC-WE. Driven by our curiosity and a passion for design, we wanted to create something that makes players think, question, and reflect. Our game Psykiosk is the result of our shared ideas, playful experimentations, and desire to explore moral choices together.

METAMORPHOSIS

A cultural game jam project about identity, discovery, and self love.

Metamorphosis invites the player into a striking visual universe filled with playful interactions with prisms, colors, and markers of identity. The game explores themes such as freedom, identity, and self-confidence. The main character is a small bird, created by Team Puzlerne, symbolizing freedom and the struggle to find it—an image of “learning to fly,” or learning to be oneself.

The player follows the bird through five levels, each representing a step on the journey of self-discovery. Along the way, the bird encounters challenges that can only be overcome by acquiring new abilities and believing in itself. The game begins on the dark, eerie forest floor and ends at the top of a great, colorful, and radiant Tree of Life.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Puzlerne, four young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks.

Mothworks is an independent game studio driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

ART X GAME

Metamorphosis is inspired by three artworks from ARoS: Your Condensation by Olafur Eliasson, Marilyn Monroe by Andy Warhol, and House of Dionysus by Sif Itona Westerberg. These works shaped the game's themes and expression—confronting one's own reflection, how colors transform our perception of the world, and the fluidity of identity. The visual style also reflects the artworks: Warhol's color shifts appear in the aesthetics and the character's journey from grey to color, while Westerberg's sculpture inspired the Tree of Life and the ascent from forest floor to treetop.

Access the game

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Puzlerne are Abtin Amin Marashi, Gaia Elisabeth Mikkelsen, Oliver Oak Stauenberg Orth, and Maren Valentin. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of Metamorphosis.

"I've attended many Game Jams before, and when I saw there was one at ARoS, I naturally wanted to join. I'm very interested in both art and games, so this Game Jam was a perfect fit for me," says Maren Valentin.

"It was a combination of my passion for game development and the chance to meet others who share the same interest as me that motivated me to take part," explains Oliver Oak.

The game studio Mothworks joined to further develop Metamorphosis in close collaboration with Team Puzlerne. Based in Aarhus, Mothworks focuses on creating unique, artistic, and eye-catching interactive experiences.

Amalie Kae, director, producer and writer at Mothworks says, *"Taking such direct inspiration from very specific cultural heritage works at ARoS has been a very interesting creative constraint, and we personally think it's made the design of Metamorphosis better."*

PsyKiosk is a point-and-click ethics adventure game that forces players to make difficult ethical choices—only to realize that no matter their actions, the end result is the same. The game provokes thought about fairness, ethics, and the illusion of choice, engaging players in a narrative where ethics is not black and white.

PsyKiosk stands out by using psychological tension in decision-making. Instead of rewarding “good” or “bad” choices, the game highlights moral ambiguity. Through aesthetic and interactive elements, the game distorts the player’s expectations, making them question their own values.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 404, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and the game was later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks. Mothworks is an independent game studio based in Aarhus and driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

INTERVIEW

Behind Team 404 are Clara Bille Tvedt, Vilma Lyng Kristensen, Mads Almdal Rasmussen and Safine Legaard Kastrupsen. They participated in 2025 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of PsyKiosk.

"When we developed our idea, we were very focused on the theme of fairness, and on what 'fair' even really means in an unfair world. We wanted the game itself to feel unfair, so that players were pushed to reflect on their own moral choices. Is choosing the 'right' thing still morally right if it leads to a bad outcome? Does intention matter more than the result?" Says Safine.

The game studio Mothworks joined later to develop PsyKiosk further. Mothworks focuses on creating unique and artistic interactive experiences.

Anne Schulin, co-founder and art leader of Mothworks says; "The themes and moral of the original game comes through in a really effective and clever way through the gameplay, and that really excited me about Psykiosk. The core idea is super strong, and that made it fairly straight forward for us as developers to just build on top of what was already there."

FROM ART TO GAME

"Our game was strongly inspired by Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's installation Colony Howl. The mix of cultures, the almost post-apocalyptic atmosphere, and the physical feeling of walking through the space really stayed with us. Even the name PsyKiosk comes from the small kiosk in the artwork, combined with the psychedelic atmosphere we felt while exploring the installation." Says Safine Legaard Kastrupsen from the original game jam team, Team 404. The artwork reflects a dystopian, cyberpunk-inspired world that has shaped Team 404's creative vision for the PsyKiosk game.

Access the game

FEATURED GAMES

Hilversum

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

At Hilversum Cultural Hub, we are working on the next step for two games: Viral Spiral and Smith and the Storm. We chose these titles because they are easy to play but also offer something to learn from. Dropstuff made an initial selection. We looked at which projects best fit our way of working: accessible, creative, and with fun as a priority. Afterwards, we presented this to the entire Cultural Hub and made the final choice.

We work in short sprints and simply try things out. Students participate from the beginning, provide feedback, help build, and contribute to improving the games. In addition, we involve other experts in our process, so we can strengthen each other. The atmosphere is open and energetic. Everyone is allowed to speak up or try things out, which makes the process lively. Sometimes things move quickly, sometimes we scrap something, but there is always movement. The games have meanwhile grown considerably: richer in content, more extensive, and simply more fun to play.

FEATURED GAMES

SMITH
and the
STORM

When the Water Returns

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

The Creators of Immersive Arts and Interactive Experiences.

DROPTUFF MEDIA is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences. DROPTUFF MEDIA conceptualizes, realizes and presents interactive media projects, audiovisual productions and educational programs for cultural, governmental and commercial partners.

Through exciting new experiences, DROPTUFF MEDIA translates messages and stories to a broad audience. By applying new techniques we aim to increase public outreach and participation.

Team behind Smith and the Storm

A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room. This game was created by Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul, third-year CMD students from the Immersive Design specialisation at Utrecht University of Applied Sciences, who worked together during the 4th EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Team behind Viral Spiral

Viral Spiral was inspired by how quickly fake news spreads, and how important it is to spot what is real. We linked this to EU press freedom because we were curious how anyone can share news, but filtering fakes can also limit that freedom. The team included Beyzanur Aslan, Floor Pasma, Sophie More and Tim Keizer, third-year CMD students at the University of Applied Sciences Amsterdam from the Creative Research Minor, formed for the 3rd EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Viral Spiral

Welcome to Viral Spiral, the board game where you, as an influencer, surf through a whirlwind of real and fake news!

Your feed is overflowing with posts, but not everything can be trusted. It's up to you to separate the facts from the fakes:

Real news? Share it proudly with your followers.
Fake news? Report it... or casually swipe it away.

The better your choices, the faster you gain extra followers. Every correct move pushes you further upward, until you reach unprecedented heights.

Make the right call, keep your feed clean, climb to the top, and beat the rest.
GO VIRAL!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 6, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. The game was later matured in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

INTERVIEW

Team 6 is Tim, Floor, Beyza and Sophie. They joined the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, Netherlands in April 2024 and developed the original prototype for Viral Spiral.

When asked about the process of developing the game, the team shares: *“The decision to center the game on misinformation and media literacy came from the growing relevance of these issues in today’s society. By making the game interactive and challenging, we wanted players to experience the dilemma of dealing with news they might encounter online.”*

DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game. Here they share their experience working on the game:

“The development of our game focused on creating a highly topical experience that can evolve over time. We actively involved students in the process, encouraging participation and hands-on data collection. Through continuous iteration, we refined the concept and deliberately involved external participants to generate valuable feedback and improve the overall design.”

GAME INSPIRATION

The game is inspired by a visit to The Mediamuseum in Hilversum. The students say: *“We were inspired by a game focused on media manipulation and fake news and how this influences us. Seeing how media has been used as a tool for propaganda made us think about the power of news in shaping societies and the potential dangers of misinformation. This sparked the idea for Viral Spiral.”* The game aligns with the EU values of democracy, freedom of expression, and access to reliable information. This game serves as a tool for educating players on how misinformation spreads and the consequences of sharing it.

Access the game

SMITH

and the

STORM

When the Water Returns

SMITH and the STORM

It is the dead of night. A raging storm lashes the coast and the water keeps rising. Hotel Smith, usually a safe haven for travelers, has become an island of stone and wood, surrounded by churning water. Roads have vanished, dikes have burst. You are trapped together with other guests, scattered across different rooms of the hotel. There is only one hope left: an old emergency transmitter at the reception desk.

Rescue services are heading out, but they don't know who is still trapped here. Only if you can work together to transmit the correct distress signal can a rescue boat reach you before the water floods the hotel. But time is running out. The transmitter is damaged. Information is scattered across different rooms. No single team has everything. Only by working together can you survive.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Orange: Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul who took part in the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. Later, the game was further developed in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, The Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

GAME INSPIRATION

“A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room,” says Team Orange.

The game incorporates the value of human dignity, as the game is about cooperation between different people even in scary situations. The game focuses on the importance of helping others despite the subtle differences between us.

Access the game

INTERVIEW

Team Orange joined the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, The Netherlands in September 2025 and developed the original prototype for Smith and the Storm.

Here they share the process of developing the prototype:

“Our prototype exists out of a maquette of the entire escape room and a few puzzles to showcase what you would do inside the escape room. We decided to make a maquette of the escape room, to show our vision of how we wanted it to look if we were to ever turn this into a real escape room.”

The game studio DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game. When asked about their experience of working on the game, they say:

“Our design process focused on making cultural heritage relevant in a contemporary context. The initial ideas and direction were largely driven by students, which we then built upon and further developed. A key challenge was translating these ideas into an engaging game design. Throughout the process, young creators were involved and provided valuable feedback that helped shape and refine the final concept.”

FEATURED GAMES

Óbidos

Professional Development of Four Featured Games with Culture

At Óbidos Cultural Hub, the selection of the two games to be matured (Puss in Books and Criminal Fauna Identification) happened after the second game jam, so that there was a fair amount of time to improve them. The selection process included every Cultural Hub partner, including youth, so that the selected games made sense from every partner's perspective. They should be fun, creative, and culturally relevant/informative, while having direct or indirect commercial potential.

However, some of the games that resulted from the third game jam were acclaimed in those same respects, and there was a feeling of missed opportunity for not including them in the selection. After some analysis by the Cultural Hub's CI partner, BATTLESHEEP, it was decided that two more games could move forward with the maturing process, adding Blue Brigade and Bufo Catcher to the lot.

Given the relatively high quality of the four selected games, BATTLESHEEP decided to enquire the original authors if they would like to be involved in the maturing process, working as game designers, programmers, artists, and audio producers, while receiving professional support and following industry practices. Every participant enthusiastically agreed, as it gave them an opportunity to remain attached to their creations while evolving professionally.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

BATTLESHEEP

BATTLESHEEP is a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, focused on both independent and work-for-hire projects.

Founded as a side-project in 2008 by a team of industry professionals with multi-platform experience, it quickly evolved into an established game studio.

We have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences.

We started out developing casual and advergames for clients, while simultaneously publishing our own original titles.

More recently we have been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Team behind Blue Brigade

Our jam team was named “Ovo Escalfado” (Poached Egg). A very diverse group of people, each with their specialty. Artists (Daniel Fernandes and Gabriela Branco), programmers (António Rodrigues and Tomás Franco), a concept artist (Lorena Bueno), and a sound designer (Tiago Lourenço).

Team behind Criminal Feather Identification

Hi there! The original team for C.F.I. is made up of a small group of first year students in Lusofona’s Videogames bachelor's, both artists and programmers, brought together during the second EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam at Óbidos. Our group included Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues.

Team behind Puss In Books

Hey! We are team “Ovo Cozido” (Boiled Egg) and we created the game Puss in Books! On our team we have just 2 people, a programmer (António) and an artist (Gabriela). Together we love making games and participating in game jams!

Team behind Mole Catcher

Hello! We are “Ovo Estrelado” (Fried Egg), the team behind Mole Catcher. We are composed of a programmer, a pixel artist, and a game designer/pixel character artist, although we all shared some of the game design tasks. We came together by chance and have been working on other projects together since!

Blue Brigade is a small game made by six people, where you play as a PIDE agent during the Portuguese restricting regime, in the town of Óbidos and armed with the regime's iconic blue pencil. At first, it feels light and playful as you run around censoring people who break the rules.

But as you notice the banned clothes, forbidden music, and silenced conversations, the tone shifts, and the village begins to lose its colors. Behind the cute art and simple tasks, the game quietly shows the weight of living under censorship.

GAME CREATORS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Escalfado, six young people who participated in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos and it was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

GAME INSPIRATION

When the theme of the game jam was announced, the Carnation Revolution of 1974, a lot of ideas immediately came to mind. A knight wielding a black censor bar and hitting people with it to censor them. As the theme was explored more closely and the historical context was examined, the ideas shifted toward something more authentic. Instead of a censor bar, the tool actually used at the time, the blue pencil, was introduced, making it fitting for the player to take the role of an agent from that era. Further research into the period revealed what people were forbidden to talk about, the clothing styles that were banned, and the music and books that were censored.

Access the game

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Escalfado (Poached Egg) are Daniel Fernandes, Gabriela Branco, António Rodrigues, Tomás Franco, Lorena Bueno and Tiago Lourenço. When asked about the experience Daniel says: *“An exciting teamwork project that allowed us to develop a remarkable game while also learning a lot about Óbidos’ culture and history.”*

“A funny and at times stressful project that really pushed our creativity, with stretchy character animations that gave the whole game a unique, quirky charm,” explains António.

“A cute and ironic art style packed with earthy tones, sketchy line art, and round characters that make up for the realistic historic time and tough situation it presents,” says Lorena.

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: *“It’s incredible that a game with this depth and charm was the product of a game jam. It is challenging and fun to play, it looks amazing, and has layers of details that you unveil only through multiple playthroughs.”*

In Puss In Books, you embark on a journey guiding a kitty through a whimsical journey as it explores dreams inspired by Óbidos' legends. Traverse a literary world and craft an enchanting narrative as the cat travels through the captivating scenarios within its dreams.

Experience a blend of imagination and adventure, where each dream unveils new challenges and discoveries in a quest to uncover the essence of literary magic. With this game, we hope to offer a small taste of Óbidos through typography, books, and hopefully cats!

GAME CREATORS

The original prototype game was created by Team Ovo Cozido, two young people who took part in the first Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos, in February 2024. Puss In Books was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

GAME INSPIRATION

The game takes inspiration from Scribblenauts and the way its puzzles interact with the environment around the player. The idea came from an excursion trip to Óbidos, where a visit to a typography shop included an introduction to the craft of printing and the process of imprinting shapes and letters onto paper. This inspired the idea for a writing game. While strolling around Óbidos and seeing kitty after kitty in the streets, lying in stores and at libraries, the main character had to be a kitty. The current version of the game took inspiration from the Óbidos legend "Door of Betrayal".

Access the game

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Cozido are António Rodrigues, a programmer, and Gabriela Branco, an artist. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos under the theme "Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature," where they created the first prototype of Puss In Books.

When asked about the experience António says: "It was a lot of fun to work on and to visit the town and to make a small cozy game about a cat living through stories."

Gabriela continues, "Óbidos was an inspiring experience we will carry for life."

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop Puss In Books. BATTLESHEEP have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: "Living proof of what a small, talented team can accomplish in a very short time with the right focus. Being so content-heavy, this was a risky project to do in a game jam context. Yet here it is for everyone to experience."

In the Óbidos Lagoon, several crimes occur throughout the year. From stealing someone's precious items to well-prepared murder scenes. The culprits? Birds! Play as a detective and find out who did the atrocities in the case files. Arrest those feathery criminals and earn yourself a promotion!

This game was made with the objective of offering, through some ridiculous designs and laidback aesthetics, a way to teach or promote interest in the lagoon's fauna and other dynamics within this ecosystem.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues. Six young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. The game was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

YOU WERE WRONG.

Access the prototype

INTERVIEW

The team behind Criminal Feather Identification participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2024, where they created the first prototype originally called Criminal Fauna Identification. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: *“The Óbidos Game Jam was an unforgettable experience! Turning birds into characters was an interesting adventure, making them look somewhat resembling a criminal while keeping them true to their living counterparts was a captivating challenge,”* says João. Mariana continues, *“The jam was an experience that I wouldn't have the opportunity to have at any other time. I was inexperienced then, but participating pushed me and helped me build a habit to keep creating. I felt much more confident in my skills, which enabled me to have fun finishing this project.”* The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. *“A lot of research went into this game, with the team pushing hard to keep it playful, funny, informative, and replayable. The true meaning of team effort and dedication,”* says Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP.

GAME INSPIRATION

The main inspiration was a game called “Time Waster”, where you have to connect simplified crime descriptions to mugshots of human criminals. The theme of the Cultural Game Jam was “Óbidos Lagoon”, and who better represents it than its residents, the avifauna? In the game, all the criminals are native birds from the Óbidos Lagoon. Following their habits and lifestyle, they perform crimes inspired by their way of living and eating habits. All suspects in the game were kept as birds to make it harder to dismiss the innocent ones. The game “Papers, Please” was also an inspiration, in the way the information is presented to the player through different files.

Access the game

Mole Catcher

You are transported back to 1974 Portugal, which is under the regime of a dictatorship. You are stationed in the small town of Óbidos as a revolutionary tasked with keeping check of who enters the village's iconic theatre, which is home to a crucial meeting for the upcoming revolution, meant to overthrow the dictatorship!

However, you are informed that moles are trying to infiltrate the meeting. It is your job to check documents and compare information to find out who the moles are!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Estrelado, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. Behind Team Ovo Estrelado are Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Júlia Costa and Tiago Lourenço. Mole Catcher was later matured in collaboration with the game studio BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal.

Original prototype

Access the prototype

INTERVIEW

Team Ovo Estrelado participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2025, where they created the first prototype of Mole Catcher, originally called Bufo Catcher. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: “Everything in the playable area was idealized with the intent of making the player feel like they were truly living that role of a guard in 1974,” says Cátia. “To truly immerse the player, we tried our best to find real-life information that was used at the time,” says Maria. “We wanted to convey to the player the sense of secrecy and fear the Portuguese people faced during the harsh years of the Estado Novo,” Júlia says. “The worry of being constantly watched and spied on and that every action you took might get judged by an authority and even get you arrested.”

Later in the process the game studio BATTLESHEEP joined to further develop the game. Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: “Disguised as a simple game, this is a true gem of an idea. Shedding light on true events, it particularly speaks to the hearts of those who lived through the Portuguese regime and, later, the revolution.”

GAME INSPIRATION

The theme behind the Cultural Game Jam was the Portuguese Carnation Revolution and the jam took place in the town of Óbidos. That was a good opportunity to make the game be set in the town and highlight this aspect of the preparations for the revolution that has been overshadowed and is widely unknown. The main inspiration was the game “Papers, Please”, as that was the best format to show military artifacts and objects of that time and the grime and overwhelming pressure that was felt during the dictatorship. “Small nods to the time in which the game took place, were the artistic choices in things like, for example, the character sprites, whose artistic direction was inspired by the colors and proportions used by famous Portuguese painters who lived through the dictatorship,” says Maria Sequeira.

Access the game

INTRODUCTION

THE CULTURAL GAME PROTOTYPES

During the EPIC-WE project we have hosted **12 Cultural Game Jams** - 4 from the Óbidos Cultural Hub in Portugal, 4 from the Hilversum Cultural Hub in the Netherlands, and 4 from the Aarhus Cultural Hub in Denmark.

Here, **424 young people** (between 15-25) have worked together in teams to create **117 Cultural Game Prototypes**. Either as **games through culture** - working directly with culture as material for game-making - or as **games for culture** - exploring or interpreting heritage and values through game-making that aim for critical reflection, civic engagement, or cultural transformation.

From these cultural game prototypes each Cultural Hub selected two or more of the teams games to be further developed into a featured game with culture through close collaboration between youth and the three Cultural Hub's game studios - showing how games working with culture can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture. In total 8 Featured EPIC-WE Games was developed during the project.

For the EPIC-WE Legacies Event a broad selection of the 117 Cultural Game Prototypes was curated by each

Cultural Hub to be showcased at ARoS Art Museum and Filmby Aarhus as one of the big legacies of the project. For the Games through Culture EXPO at ARoS Art Museum, 18 games were selected and showcased and for the Games for Culture EXPO at Filmby Aarhus, 20 games were selected and showcased.

This is the legacy of young people taking up game-making as a form of culture-making - the result of which you find in this D5.2 Demonstrator. This collection contains and presents all the Cultural Game Prototypes . Together they illustrate the power of young people's cultural-creative thinking with heritage and values and the potential of Cultural Game Jams inviting young people to game jam with cultural heritage themes, sites, collections, archives, artworks, values, and identities.

In this following collection we celebrate all of the young people that are the beating and empowered heart of our epic-we - we hope they inspire you like they have inspired us! Enjoy reading about the 117 Cultural Game Prototypes!

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

ABOUT AARHUS CULTURAL GAME JAM #1

The first Aarhus CGJ took place on February 3–4, 2024, inside the permanent exhibition Human Nature at ARoS, Scandinavia’s most visited art museum and CHI partner of EPIC-WE. Human Nature presents an exploration of the human condition through themes of philosophy, religion, exploration, and landscape, inviting visitors to reflect on humanity’s relationship with nature and technology in a changing world. This curatorial framing provided a rich context for the CGJ, where twenty-three youth participants were encouraged to reinterpret selected artworks as interactive, playable experiences. Working directly within the exhibition space, surrounded by the artworks themselves, participants created five original game prototypes that translated visual art into participatory and narrative forms.

Aarhus CGJ1

Date: February 3–4, 2024

Location: ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 2 days

Participants: 23 youth (ages 15–27, open recruitment)

Number of Games: 5 prototypes

Theme: Human Nature (Golden Age artworks from ARoS’ permanent collection)

ART PARABLE

Created by: Em Hansen, London Patterson, Niel Nielsen and Marie Louise Bachmann
Inspired by: Vilhelm Kyhn's painting "Vejle Fjord"
Building on: Freedom & Rule of Law
Find game [here](#).

Reimagine Danish art through a modern lens, revealing hidden historical narratives.

"Art Parable" recontextualizes Danish art from the 1800s, exploring cultural history through a remix of artistic traits. Re-create Vilhelm Kyhn's "Vejle Fjord" with a modern twist, engaging with historical narratives and European values of freedom and law through interactive gameplay.

GOOSE ON THE LOOSE

Created by: William, Noah, Liv and Lucas
Inspired by: Johannes Larsen's painting 'Ten Brent Geese on the Shore' (1921)
Buidling on: Freedom
Find game [here](#).

Immerse yourself in childlike imagination.

We have aimed to create a sense of peace, albeit through the eyes of a goose. A relaxing world to truly immerse yourself in, with fun gameplay and the freedom to move wherever you want. Establishing the feeling of a free world and a free imagination, Goose on the Loose incorporates small elements of philosophy and a calming atmosphere.

ROOMINATION

Created by: Oscar, Soren and Adem

Inspired by: Vilhelm Hammershøi's paintings in 'the exhibition 'Human Nature' (1889-1911)

Buiding on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Even when you are close to freedom, you can't always reach it.

With inspiration from the Danish painter Vilhelm Hammershøi, celebrated for his poetic portraits and interiors, 'Roomination' sets a tranquil scene in atmospheric environments reminiscent of his art and color palette. Experience the interplay of light and shadow, contemplate about solitude, and discover the beauty of everyday moments.

CREATE YOUR LEGACY

Created by: Maha Farid Majid, Tomasnuclear, Maja Børsting Lund, Mark Oliver Sandfeld Nielsen, Beinta Brynhildardóttir Egholm and Rikke Gehrke Jensen

Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Who shapes history and cultural heritage?

In this game you interact with Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Aarhus 31 May 1849'. You play as an artist risking your life while sketching cavalries fighting, overlooking the battlefield, dodging bullets and swords; while painting an art piece you hope to become your future legacy, and a testament to your heroic act.

BLISS

Created by: Leonard Hjuler Baungaard, Maya Stuckert, Emilie Lykkegaard Schmidt and Patrizia Bjertrup-Röben

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Vilhelm Kyhn's painting 'View at Vejle Fjord' (1862)

Find game [here](#).

Escape to nature and balance resources.

Escape to nature and balance resources in this anti-expansionist game. "Bliss" is about escaping modern society to live in balance with nature. Manage resources wisely as the expansion comes with a price. Collect resources in a forest, with the environment reacting to your actions.

ABOUT AARHUS CULTURAL GAME JAM #2

The second CGJ in Aarhus, Denmark (CGJ2) brought together 39 youth participants for a weekend of co-creating games rooted in cultural heritage on September 7–8, 2024. Hosted at ARoS, participants explored and drew inspiration from tangible cultural heritage within the modern era, reinterpreting artworks through innovative game-making that reflected and engaged with the heritage collections. The Aarhus Cultural Hub CGJ2 focused on contemporary and postmodern artworks within ARoS Collection: 1960 - now, with museum facilitators guiding participants through interpretation and cultural reflection.

Date: September 7–8, 2024

Location: ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 2 days

Participants: 39 youth participants (open recruitment plus one secondary school class)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes

Theme: Contemporary and postmodern artworks, ARoS Collection: 1960 - now

PARTY HORSE

Inspired by: Collection at ARoS

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Find the chameleon in a word game of deduction and bluffing. Outsmart your friends to win.

In "PartyHorse", players select a gamemaster who assigns words related to the exhibition theme. One player is a "chameleon" with a different word and must blend in while the others try to identify them.

The game involves deduction and bluffing, with a joker role adding complexity for extra challenge.

METAMORPHOSIS

Created by: Maren, Oliver, Aptin and Gaia

Inspired by: Your condensation by Olafur Eliasson, Marilyn Monroe by Andy Warhol, House of Dionysus by Sif Itona Westerberg

Buidling on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Fight Doubt-Monsters and explore identity. Progress through self-doubt and discovery to gain new skills.

In "Metamorphosis", you play as a bird-like character battling Doubt-Monsters while exploring identity. The game involves picking up new skills as you face stages of self-doubt and discovery, reflecting on personal growth and transformation.

GRIND THE WORLD

Created by: Mikkel Ugilt, Kostya Milkevich and Victoria Elle Bache

Inspired by: Hanne Nielsen & Birgit Johnsen's video performance 'Peeling Onions' (1995)

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Grind disturbing items or refuse.

From household objects to a puppy or a baby, this thought-provoking game asks the player to grind increasingly disturbing items.

The game explores ethical decisions in gameplay: Players have the freedom to refuse, making them reflect on mindless gaming behavior and the consequences of their actions.

KILL THE BLUE GUYS (NO GASLIGHT EDITION)

Created by: Silaz, Milo, Lisa, Gustav

Inspired by: Collection at ARoS

Buidling on: Human Dignity

Find game [here](#).

Shoot blue characters before time runs out. A critique of racism through fast-paced action.

In "Kill the Blue Guys", you play as a red character with a gun, shooting blue characters in various rooms. Inspired by an exhibition, the game explores the harmful effects of racism. The goal is to shoot the blue characters before time runs out, but the underlying message critiques racial prejudice.

ARCHY

Created by: Tom Frodsham, Joachim Sørensell, Haoming Yang, Eureka Wang
Inspired by: Collection at ARoS
Building on: Human Dignity
Find game [here](#).

In 2300, recover artifacts from the 2020s with AI help. Discover and interpret the relics of a forgotten era.

Set in 2300, you are an archaeologist tasked with recovering objects from the 2020s after a mysterious event. Using AI assistance, identify six historical artifacts. "Archy" is about discovery and interpretation of these relics.

APHASIA

Created by: Alexander, Aran, Hazel, Jakob and Oscar
Building on: Human dignity and freedom
Inspired by: Christian Lemmerz' sculpture 'Aphasia II' (1986)
Find game [here](#).

Explore repetitive life and human dignity.

Reflect on mundane routines and discover what makes life worthwhile. 'Aphasia' examines the repetitive nature of life and questions human dignity and freedom. The player experiences a cycle of everyday tasks that blur reality. We want the players to reflect on their own life, to think about what parts of their life are most meaningful.

ESCAPE HORSE

Created by: William

Inspired by: Bjørn Nørgaard's artwork
"Hesteofringen"

Building on: Human Dignity

Find game [here](#).

A game inspired by Bjørn Nørgaard's artwork "Hesteofringen".

The game is called "Escape Horse". It draws inspiration from the exhibition 1960 to Now and is heavily influenced by Bjørn Nørgaard's artwork "Hesteofringen".

The game revolves around solving a horse's murder. You find a horse's head and must locate the rest of the horse.

HESTEKRAFT

Created by: Jonas, Mathias, Line and Buster

Inspired by: Bjørn Nørgaard's artwork
"Hesteofringen"

Buidling on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Gain horse powers with both benefits and drawbacks. Win by racing to the end or embracing your new horse life.

In "Hestekraft", players choose whether to accept horse powers, which have both positive and negative effects, as they progress. You can win by reaching the end first or by fully transforming into a horse and embracing your new life. The game reflects on the freedom to choose one's path.

DRIVE BY

Created by: Nicklas, Valdemar, Lea, Nikolaj and Markus

Inspired by: 'Sawdy nr. 46' by Edward Kienholz

Building on: Democracy

Find game [here](#).

**Escape reality in this side-scroller.
Dodge obstacles while ignoring the
conflicts outside your car window.**

"Drive By" is a side-scroller where the player uses escapism to avoid reality. Inspired by artworks, the game highlights how people ignore responsibilities. The character drives through various environments while dodging obstacles in a mini-game within the car window. The radio describes the conflicts that are being ignored.

ABOUT AARHUS CULTURAL GAME JAM #3

The third Aarhus CGJ took place on March 3–7, 2025, as the ninth edition of the EPIC-WE project. This week-long event brought together 45 first-year Digital Design students from Aarhus University for an intensive creative process that combined cultural exploration, contemporary art, and societal reflection.

This CGJ was set across three venues: ARoS Aarhus Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University. The CGJ created diverse and inspiring environments for play, design, and reflection. Guided by the glocal theme *That's Not Fair!*, participants explored fairness and inequality as fundamental forces shaping society. The CGJ Brief encouraged students to address issues such as economic disparity, social inclusion, and climate justice. The goal was to design value-sensitive cultural games (games for culture) that provoke playful, critical, and empathetic conversations about what fairness means to youth in Europe today.

Date: March 3–7, 2025

Location: ARoS, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University in Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 5 days across one week

Participants: 45 first-year Digital Design students (ages 20-32) from Aarhus University

Number of Games: 11 prototypes

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture)

ESCAPING REALITY

Created by: Mikkel, Emilie, Kajsa and Camilla
Inspired by: “Dawn hours in the neighbour’s house”
by Pippilotti Rist
Building on: Freedom
Find game [here](#).

This is a game about staying inside and looking at your TV.

You're home, watching television. The screen floods with images of disaster, like wars, crises, collapse. You seem powerless, stuck in your apartment. But are you really? Can you change anything? Is the world on screen worse than the one outside your walls? This game challenges your perception of reality, control, and the comfort of inaction.

THE CORRIDOR

Created by: Astrid Louise, Rebeca, Julian, Frederik, Lin
Inspired by: Jonah Freeman and Justin Lowe, “Colony Howl”
Buidling on: Democracy & Freedom
Find game [here](#).

Lead the nation, face the cost.

The year is 1984. You've just become the leader of a nation on the brink of change, but your rise was far from clean. A shadowy deal secured your power. Now, standing at the edge of history, you must shape the future. Every decision has a cost. Will you choose free speech or control? Reform or repression? Power is yours, but so are the consequences.

PERCEPTION

Created by: Demet Temel, Yasmina Chami, Emilia Nordtømme, Sebastian Poulsen
Inspired by: Collection at ARoS
Building on: Freedom & Equality
Find game [here](#).

"Perception" challenges the illusion of free choice, questioning how cultural norms shape our decisions. Through visuals, sound, and feedback, it blurs the lines between "right" and "wrong", without clear answers.

Dare to challenge your own perception? Play and join the discussion.

YOUR FILTERED LIFE

Created by: Maria, August, Mathilde and Marthea
Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011)
Building on: Equality and freedom
Find game [here](#).

Make the right decisions and shape your future!

You've just turned 18 and gained your independence. Every choice matters, some small, some life-changing. Our game explores themes of equality and freedom through roleplay, highlighting how both personal choices and the luck of one's starting position shape opportunities, just like in real life.

KNOW YOUR NEIGHBOR(?)

Created by: Petra, Ingrid, Alma, Nicoline and Astrid

Building on: Equality

Inspired by: Pippilotti Rist's installation 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005)

Find game [here](#).

Are you aware of your own prejudices?

Access the game

In this puzzle game players are told to identify objects that don't belong in a Danish apartment. The game explores equality, prejudice, and how culture is shared across society through unconscious biases, passed down from generation to generation. Our hope is for players to be aware of their own prejudices as well as to encourage dialog.

SEND ANOTHER CREW

Created by: Kalle, Christian, Jonas, Mille and Jonas

Building on: Human dignity

Inspired by: Pippilotti Rist's 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005) and Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's 'Colony Howl' (2022)

Find game [here](#).

You pray to your gods that it all goes smoothly.

Access the game

The year is 2125. It is your first day as a mechanics assistant on board a submarine, owned by Big Gordon Corp. You are on a mission to a city flooded by rising sea levels, to deliver some cargo. Sail through the dark waters of a dystopian future, while experiencing the consequences of an unequal power hierarchy.

US & THEM

Created by: Hannah, Kasper, Tobias and Frederik
Building on: Human dignity
Inspired by: James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002) and Pipilotti Rist's 'Dawn Hours in the Neighbour's House' (2005)
 Find game [here](#).

Will you survive the night?

Backstory

You have been busy lately at your crappy corporate day-time job. You have been procrastinating your house chores for long enough. So you decide that you going to pull an all nighter to get them done.

The landlord just called you to inform you that someone new is to move into the adjacent empty apartment in a week or so. The landlord seems slightly off, and quickly ends the call.

Access the game

nothing of it, and make your way to your complex. You spot some weird looking boxes sitting outside the hallway.

Survive the night, as you help the main character completing his household chores and fulfilling his basic needs while spying on the neighbor. The game explores neighborhood and paranoia in an eerie, unsettling atmosphere that distorts reality. Through horror, the game highlights the discomfort of villainizing or "othering" the neighbor.

PSYKIOSK

Created by: Vilma, Clara, Mads, Safine
Inspired by: Jonah Freeman and Justin Lowe, "Colony Howl"
Buidling on: Rule of Law
 Find game [here](#).

"PsyKiosk" is a point-and-click morality adventure where players face tough ethical choices, only to discover the outcome remains unchanged.

The game challenges perceptions of fairness, ethics, and the illusion of choice, blurring the lines between right and wrong.

GET IN

Created by: Simon, Mads Emil, Sebastian
Inspired by: Jonah Freeman and Justin Lowe, "Colony Howl"
Building on: Equality
Find game [here](#).

Welcome to Equitasia! Good luck getting in.

"GET IN" is a darkly absurd quiz game where you try to enter a dystopian alternate reality by completing an impossible citizenship test.

Questions are surreal, answers are unfair, and the system is rigged against you. Inspired by brutalist aesthetics, retro tech, and real-world bureaucracy, the game explores human dignity, exclusion, and the illusion of choice in oppressive systems.

THE GAME OF INFLUENCE

Created by: Sofie Østerby Spielberg, Florentina Bujupai, Evelyn Denise Lencina Rosales and Sofie Bredahl
Building on: Human dignity, equality and freedom
Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011), James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002) and Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's 'Colony Howl' (2022)
Find game [here](#).

Confront invisible forces that govern social life.

Players are dropped into a social simulation, where every choice they make affects their inclusion or exclusion from a group. Assigned a random identity – complete with background, income, and beliefs – they must navigate a judgmental dinner party setting, uncovering how social bias, privilege, and unspoken norms shape who gets to belong.

A WEEK OF WAR

Created by: Sigrid, Evian and Julie

Building on: Democracy

Inspired by: Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011) and James Turrell's 'Milkrun III' (2002)

Find game [here](#).

Democracy is suspended, every choice is yours alone.

Step into the role of Denmark's supreme leader for a week of war. You have seven days to secure power and stabilize the nation. Democracy is suspended; every choice is yours alone. Will you lead your people with freedom or dominate with force? Your legacy depends on how far you're willing to go. In the end, power is the price of survival.

ABOUT AARHUS CULTURAL GAME JAM #4

The fourth Aarhus CGJ, held between March and May 2025, marked the final iteration of the EPIC-WE CGJ series. Designed as a slow jam spanning six weeks, the event linked ARoS Art Museum, Aarhus University (AU), and Filmby Aarhus through a sequence of structured sessions grounded in the glocal theme “Heritage Remixed.”

ARoS’s Human Nature collection was selected as the creative foundation for the CGJ, offering public-domain artworks with strong narrative potential, including romanticised landscapes, social scenes, and symbolic objects that inspired themes such as propaganda, consumerism, and cultural revisionism. Participants explored how public-domain artworks at ARoS could be reimagined as playable cultural heritage experiences that link tangible heritage with European values and contemporary issues such as consumerism, freedom, and belonging. The format emphasised games through culture, positioning creative reinterpretation as a form of cultural participation where tangible heritage becomes concrete game-making material.

Building on earlier iterations, this CGJ introduced an extended focus on XR technologies, encouraging participants to use augmented and virtual reality as tools for cultural expression.

Date: March 21 – May 9, 2025

Location: ARoS Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University, Denmark

Duration: 6 weeks (slow jam across alternating sessions)

Participants: 61 students, age 22-28 (24 Digital Design, 37 Computer Science, Aarhus University)

Number of Games: 18 prototypes

Theme: Heritage Remixed (Games through Culture), using VR/AR technologies

EVERYTHING IN MODIFICATION

Created by: Nadia Ah., Naja Hammershøj Anicka, Isabella Rosing, Simon Vieth, Mikkel Aarup Vinther
Building on: Freedom
Inspired by: Krøyer's painting "Skagensjægerne."
Find game [here](#).

What stories do our cultural artifacts really tell? Question the narrative, choose your freedom.

A virtual reality puzzle game exploring cultural narratives and freedom through Krøyer's painting "Skagensjægerne." You reassemble shattered pieces while an authoritarian voice demands the "correct" version. Multiple assembly options exist, but the narrator insists on conformity. This reverse puzzle challenges players to question cultural narratives and assert their agency against imposed interpretations.

HARVEST OF HOPE

Created by: Mai, Linn Emilie, Selma
Building on: Freedom
Inspired by: "Udvandrere på Larsens Plads" by Edvard Petersen
Find game [here](#).

A journey from dystopia to paradise through the power of optimism.

Harvest of Hope

An augmented reality experience where players collect bright oranges symbolizing hope while journeying from a dystopian present to an idyllic future. Inspired by romantic paintings and emigrant voyages, movement reveals beauty but harvesting requires confronting harsh realities. Transform your world by gathering hope, one orange at a time.

STAND WITH THEM

Created by: Yunting Wang, Wei Xiong, Yaning Wen

Building on: Human Dignity & Freedom

Inspired by: Svend Wiig Hansen "Menneskeridt"

Find game [here](#).

Confront injustice and embody human rights through augmented reality interaction.

A narrative game transforming your environment into scenes of oppression and resistance. Inspired by a painting of red giants dominating green figures, you encounter three augmented reality scenarios where armed knights force civilians into dehumanizing labor. Through dialogue choices and physical touch interactions, you decide to help, ignore, or join oppressors, shaping outcomes that explore human rights.

PLAYING GOD

Created by: Patrekur Agnarsson and Aimo Hirvonen

Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)

Building on: Equality and freedom

Find game [here](#).

Play God in a war simulation inspired by Danish art history.

A simulated battleground augmented reality game where you decide which side wins by playing God by moving soldiers, giving them weapons, or eliminating them. Inspired by Jørgen Sonne's iconic war painting, the game transforms your surroundings into a Danish-Prussian battlefield, exploring themes of equality and divine intervention in war.

Access the game

HOOKED ON HISTORY

Created by: Fanni, Anežka, Oliver

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Harald Giersing's painting "Young lady in pale blue"

Find game [here](#).

Fish for fragments, piece together history: an adventure in art restoration.

Fish pieces of paintings from a virtual lake and solve puzzles to reconstruct historical artworks. Using controller-based fishing you engage with art details you might miss in museums, learning cultural context through interactive restoration and discovery.

PORTRAIT NUMBER 13

Created by: Sayana, Jacob, Roxana

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Hammershøi paintings and general collection at ARoS

Find game [here](#).

What if the portraits from the museum could speak? Solve the mystery or become Portrait Number 13.

An augmented reality mystery-puzzle game set in a museum where portraits come alive at night, and one of them commits murder. You investigate clues, restore damaged paintings, and uncover stories of artistic suppression to identify the killer among three suspects. Inspired by historical censorship and silenced voices, failure means becoming the next portrait on the wall forever.

LET'S CERAMIC

Created by: Yunhui Song, Haiyang Xu
Building on: Freedom
Inspired by: Ceramic artworks from the ARoS Collection
Find game [here](#).

Shape, decorate, and fire your way into ceramic heritage.

An immersive game where you can bring ceramic to life through intuitive hand gestures in augmented reality. You shape virtual clay, decorate with textures from real ARoS Museum artworks, and fire their creations in a kiln. This blend of traditional craft and digital art transforms Danish ceramic techniques into a personal, culturally meaningful experience of creation and storytelling.

ASHES OR BREATH

Created by: Chengdong "Black" Sun, Ge "Kacy" Fu, Shichao Guo
Building on: Human dignity, Equality and Freedom
Inspired by: The ARoS Collection
Find game [here](#).

If everything is burning, what would you save, a living cat, or the Mona Lisa?

An augmented reality game confronting players with an irreversible choice in a burning museum: rescue a living cat or preserve the priceless Mona Lisa. This philosophical experience explores empathy, cultural heritage, and personal values through embodied decision-making, leading to a surreal VR Rewind Room where memory bubbles reveal consequences without moral judgment.

THE LOST SCROLL

Created by: Suqi Xiang, Xu Han, Jiqiang Dong
Building on: Freedom and Human Dignity
Inspired by: The ARoS Collection
Find game [here](#).

Find the clues, investigate the past and restore this painting as a tribute to European migration and freedom.

Through augmented reality investigation at a virtual desk, you piece together clues to restore a forgotten painting and discover tales of freedom, dignity, and hope in European migration history. "The Lost Scrolls" serves as a tool for education and cultural preservation, ensuring that a silenced history resonates with modern audiences.

GIERSING'S WIFE'S WRATH

Created by: Peeter Tarvas, Hans Pedersen, Johan Rubak
Building on: Freedom, Equality and Democracy
Inspired by: Harald Giersing's painting "Ung dame i lyseblåt"
Find game [here](#).

Draw to survive, escape the haunting ghost of Giersing's wife in this horror experience.

"Giersing's Wife's Wrath" is an augmented reality horror game inspired by Harald Giersing's portrait of his wife. Players must quickly trace outlined objects on a virtual canvas while a sorrowful ghost approaches. Complete drawings to reset the timer and push her away. The narrative reimagines the painting's subject as trapped by societal norms.

PICARSSO

Created by: Manos, Mate, Kamil

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: ARoS Human Nature Exhibition

Find game [here](#).

Experience art in a new dimension, where sight meets sound and creativity knows no bounds.

"PicARsso" is an augmented reality drawing game where you explore how audio environments influence artistic expression. You draw on physical canvas with Logitech MX Ink pen, inspired by ARoS Human Nature Exhibition paintings, while immersed in different soundscapes. Teams compete as one player creates and another guesses the inspiration and audio, testing the connection between sound, emotion, and creative freedom.

BRUSH HOUR

Created by: Andreas, Tim, Lauren

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: ARoS Human Nature Exhibition

Find game [here](#).

Brush away the flaws, or face the king.

BrushHour

In "Brush Hour", you're a Romantic-era painter tasked with pleasing the king. He despises anything unpleasant, so use your trusty brush to erase the bad. Reimagine the world with our handcrafted shader into a romanticized vision. But beware: reality creeps back in. Rotten trees and other flaws will pierce the illusion. Keep the corruption away, or face the king's wrath. Good luck!

RESTORY

Created by: Jakob, Johanne, Josefine, Maria and Rikke

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Gotfred Rump's View at Vejle Fjord
Find game [here](#).

Clean up culture, restore heritage, and remove overconsumption from Rump's romantic landscape.

An immersive augmented reality puzzle-adventure set within Gotfred Rump's "View at Vejle Fjord" painting. You remove modern overconsumption objects, like fast fashion, electronics, and plastic waste, scattered throughout the romantic landscape. Using tactile grab-and-remove mechanics, each disposal restores environmental harmony while reflecting on consumption habits and cultural values of thrift versus excess.

AR KINGDOMS

Created by: Eduard, Enok and Peter

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: ARoS Human Nature Exhibition
Find game [here](#).

Rule with wisdom, build with heart in this strategy game where your kingdom's fate rests in your hands.

An augmented reality strategy game where you rule as mad King Christian VII, expanding Denmark-Norway into unknown territory. Manage resources, assign citizens, and defend against mythical Slattenpatte monsters while balancing happiness and survival. Your decisions shape a utopia or dystopia, with real paintings reflecting your kingdom's cultural progress and values.

MUSEUM OF DREAMS

Created by: Morten, Peter, Mikkel, Nicolai and Victor

Inspired by: The entire 'Human Nature'-exhibition.

Building on: Equality and freedom

Find game [here](#).

Break the rules and remix culture.

A virtual reality sandbox game where players shrink to child-size in a surreal museum and remix artworks using paint guns and stickers. Inspired by European art history, players break museum rules through an empowering gameplay that challenges who get to "touch" cultural heritage, making it playful, inclusive, and co-creative.

IN SEARCH OF IDA

Created by: Maj, Lissa, Trine, Albin and Gabriel

Building on: Human dignity and Equality

Inspired by: Vilhelm Hammershøi's painting at ARoS

Find game [here](#).

What happens when someone disappears, not from life, but from history?

A short virtual reality experience where you play as an archivist researching Ida Hammershøi, the overlooked wife of Danish painter Vilhelm Hammershøi. As you explore her story through letters and photos in your archive office, something shifts, the room darkens, Ida fades from paintings. Blending cultural heritage with psychological horror, the game reclaims forgotten voices in art history.

REALITY CHECK

Created by: Christina, Caroline, Helene and Julie
Building on: Human Dignity & Equality
Inspired by: ARoS Human Nature Exhibition
Find game [here](#).

History is never truly in the past: it's a living story, shaped and reshaped by those who tell it.

A virtual reality game exploring the contrast between Romanticism's idealized world and the Modern Breakthrough's harsh reality. As a farmer struggling with dying plants, you discover a portal to a beautiful Romantic world and try to bring its sunlight back. But you'll learn that polished illusions can't nurture real growth, only truth can sustain life.

CENSORED TRUTHS

Created by: Alessandro Trotta, Simone Micalizzi and Louis Godtfred Kastrop Lindgaard
Building on: Freedom and rule of law
Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)
Find game [here](#).

For whom do you decide to speak?

An augmented reality simulation in which you're a press worker in the authoritarian republic of Naşúl. Choose what to print for an underground newsletter: will you align with the regime, or do you dare to reveal buried truths? Your choices affect public sentiment and may or may not create room for critical thinking and change.

Access the game

CULTURAL
GAME JAMS
HILVERSUM

CULTURAL
GAME JAMS
HILVERSUM

ABOUT HILVERSUM CULTURAL GAME JAM #1

The first Hilversum CGJ was held on April 13–14, 2024 at the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV) Media Museum. Over two days, 15 youth participants created games inspired by the museum’s media collection and by European values. Unlike the other cultural hubs, this CGJ began without a fixed theme. Instead, participants defined their own cultural or societal issues and connected them to European values, supported by an EUjia board designed by the research team at Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) as a facilitation tool. This approach prioritised agency, creativity, and personal relevance, positioning youth as cultural co-creators.

Hilversum CGJ1

Date: April 13–14, 2024

Location: Media Museum, Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 2 days

Participants: 15 participants, open recruitment

Number of Games: 4 prototypes

Theme: Open choice

NIJNTJE GOES BACK TO SCHOOL

Created by: Elena, Grace, Iris, Madelief, Rozin
Building on: Human Dignity
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Promote mental well-being through empathetic gameplay.

"Nijntje Goes Back to School" champions cultural values of human dignity and mental health rights, integrating community support, empathy, and resilience into gameplay. Through interactive scenarios, players confront emotional challenges, promoting empathy and emphasizing the importance of mental well-being. The game aims to evoke a range of emotions, from empathy to reassurance and strength, fostering satisfaction and highlighting collective support efforts.

CLIMATE POLITICIAN

Created by: Ronald van de Velde, Sam Philipsen, Daan Hendriks
Building on: Rule of law
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Balance industry and happiness to achieve climate goals.

In "Climate Politician," you assume the role of a leader tasked with managing your country's industry to achieve ambitious climate goals while ensuring the happiness of the population. Navigate complex decisions to strike a balance between economic progress and environmental sustainability. Implement policies, invest in green technologies, and address societal needs to foster a prosperous and eco-friendly future. Your leadership will

CAT-A-STROPHIC CLIMATE

Created by: Ash, Michelle, Quinesha

Building on: Rule of law

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Battle plastic pollution in the ocean as a team of cats.

"CAT-a-strophic Climate" immerses you in an environmental mission where you control a team of cats combating ocean plastic pollution. Choose from four unique feline characters, each armed with a Boost card for special advantages. Your objective: collect 5 pieces of trash scattered across the map and exchange them for Fish Tokens. Gather 5 Fish Tokens to secure victory and ensure your kitty's happiness and well-being. Navigate challenges, strategize with your team, and make a positive impact on the environment in this engaging and purrfect adventure.

MAKE IT...!!!

Created by: Isaiah, Tsvetelina, Angela, Rainald

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

What happens when someone disappears, not from life, but from history?

ABOUT HILVERSUM CULTURAL GAME JAM #2

The second Hilversum CGJ ran on September 9–13, 2024 and marked a significant expansion from the first event, both in scale and ambition. Hosted in collaboration with X11 secondary school in Utrecht and the Media Museum of NISV, it engaged 61 students across three classes in a week-long process that blended classroom activities with cultural immersion. Unlike the open, small-scale format of the first CGJ, CGJ2 was deliberately embedded into a school programme, providing an opportunity to reach a much broader cohort of youth under 18. The themes “Media & Democracy” and “Media & Equality” were chosen in collaboration with teachers to connect directly to curricular goals.

Hilversum CGJ2

Date: September 9–13, 2024

Location: X11 High School (Utrecht) & NISV Media Museum (Hilversum), Netherlands

Duration: 4 days, across one week

Participants: 61 secondary school students (ages 16–18)

Number of Games: 15 prototypes

Theme: Choice between Media & Democracy or Media & Equality

EPIC POLITICIAN MAKE-OVER

Created by: Sofie, Trijntje and Naomi

Building on: Equality

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Create politicians, manage resources, and build a thriving town in this political simulation.

In "Epic Politician Make-Over!", you create politicians and build your own town. Design political figures, manage resources, and guide your town's development, balancing governance and growth to build a thriving community.

BARRIO SMASHER

Created by: Zino, Ayenne, Tara and Roos

Building on: Equality and Rule of Law

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Smash or be smashed in a chaotic kitchen showdown as a fiery chef faces off against hungry Barrio!

"Barrio Smasher" is a chaotic and humorous game where a temperamental chef chases Barrio, a desperate creature who broke into an Italian restaurant to eat. As the chef, your goal is to smash Barrio, but beware—if you smash food on the counter, you lose a life. Play solo as the chef or in multiplayer, with one controlling Barrio and the other the chef, in a fast-paced kitchen showdown.

EVIE'S WORLD

Created by: Ella, Anouk and Skye

Building on: Equality

Inspired by: Pixel Games at the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Fight against global warming as the hero. Expose the inequality where the wealthy thrive while others struggle.

In "Evie's World", you play as a girl who lives in a forest and faces climate change's effects, like wildfires. You can trade resources in a market, plant seeds, and unlock features like a tool shop and seasonal crop growth.

A 60-second escape sequence shapes the game's future, offering a mix of survival and strategy.

SUPER ANIMAL

Created by: Vicky, Nora, Nora and Amber

Building on: Equality and Human Rights

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Run a supermarket for animals! Manage stock and satisfy the preferences of your quirky customers.

Manage a supermarket bustling with animal customers! In this light-hearted simulation, players stock shelves, cater to animal preferences, and keep the shop running smoothly while ensuring every creature leaves satisfied.

THE WRATH OF BENJABOEM

Created by: Bent, Luc, Freek and Dani
Building on: Equality and Rule of Law
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Destroy a zombie dictator to restore equality. Fight enemies, gather weapons, and rebel against injustice.

Destroy Benjaboem, a zombie dictator, to restore equality. Starting as a homeless person, you must navigate waves of enemies, gather weapons, and build a base to take on the final boss.

TORIK IN JAIL

Created by: Joost, Joas, Jens, Rik, Benjamin and Bart
Building on: Equality and Democracy
Inspired by: South Park installation at Sound and Vision Museum
Find game [here](#).

As President Torik, escape prison and defeat the hamster king to liberate your enslaved people.

Toria has been overtaken by hamsters, and you play as President Torik, imprisoned and fighting to escape. After freeing your people, your ultimate goal is to defeat the hamster king in combat and save the nation.

CARROT GAME

Created by: Mijntje, Myrthe, Naomi and Gwen
Building on: Equality
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

A card game about inequality, where bunnies race toward gender equality.

"Wortelspel" (Carrot Game) is a card game based on the theme of inequality, where players take on the roles of female or male bunnies. The game uses cards to determine players' actions. The objective is to achieve equality: male bunnies can take two steps at a time, while female bunnies can only take one. Special cards add strategic elements, shifting players' positions or sending them back to earlier points.

30 SECONDS POLITICS EDITION

Created by: Casper, Myrthe, Elise and Tess
Building on: Democracy and Rule of Law
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Thirty seconds to change: Climb the mountain, spark the conversation!

In "30 Seconds Politics Edition", teams of two players compete: one describes a word on a card (e.g. "Power" or "Racism"), while the other guesses. The goal is to accumulate the most points by correctly guessing the words. The game is inspired by a well-known Dutch board game called "30 seconds". Teams move up or down the mountain based on their performance.

CHALLENGES

Created by: Kyra, Aniek and Anson

Building on: Equality

Inspired by: The meme section in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Roll the dice, face the challenge, and compete in a game designed for everyone to enjoy.

"Challenges" is a game where you roll dice to determine a color, then pick a card with a challenge that varies in difficulty, awarding 1 to 3 points. You compete to win challenges and advance on the board. The game includes word-based tasks where players form words from given letters. Designed to accommodate different abilities, it ensures all players, regardless of physical skill, can participate and succeed.

DIFFERENCES & EQUALITY MEMORY

Created by: Moyra-Sophia, Silke and Jayden

Building on: Equality and Rule of Law

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Explore differences, embrace equality: a memory game against discrimination.

"Differences & Equality Memory" is a game that explores differences and equalities in everyday life. It is a memory game where you must find pairs of cards with contrasting attributes, such as "Underweight" and "Overweight" or "Rich" and "Poor". When a pair is found, you must answer a question related to a form of discrimination in everyday life.

LIFE'S A B***H

Created by: Noor, Ellis, Luna, Isabelle, Guus
Building on: Equality
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Navigate life's challenges, defy the odds, and race to the retirement home.

"Life's a B***h" is a game about equality, where you start at different socio-economic levels (rich, poor, or middle class) and face life's challenges. You can choose different paths, with some being riskier but faster, and you can even sabotage other players or steal from them. The goal is to be the first to reach the retirement home, and the game emphasizes that one's starting point does not necessarily determine their final outcome.

SPORTS & CULTURE

Created by: Youssef, Amanda, Leon, Mieke
Building on: Equality
Inspired by: Sport and the experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Choose your country, play diverse sports, and learn about culture.

In "Sports & Culture", you begin by choosing a country, which influences the sports you play and the characters you control. Compete in a variety of sports, from football and basketball to lesser-known global games. You'll also receive a "culture package" to test and expand your knowledge about your chosen country's culture.

IS IT FAIR?

Created by: Aron, Lola Tom, Famke
Building on: Equality and rule of law
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Win this game – if you can!

"Is it Fair?" is a board game that explores discrimination. You roll dice to move and, when you land on a space of your color, you draw a card. The game ends when the first player reaches the finish line, but winning is harder for non-yellow colors, raising questions about equality.

ESCAPE DE POPO

Created by: Dylan, Niklas, Kylie, Niek, Eloise
Building on: Rule of law and solidarity
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Smuggle the weapon or catch the culprit in this game that challenges critical thinking.

In "Escape the Popo", you play as either a smuggler or the police. As a smuggler, your goal is to transport a hidden weapon without being caught. As the police, you must identify the smuggler with the weapon before time runs out. You'll move across the board using dice, drawing cards to ask questions or trigger effects. With cultural themes of authority and bias, the game challenges you to strategize and think critically to win.

EQUAL GROUNDS

Created by: Dylan, Niklas, Kylie, Niek, Eloise

Building on: Rule of law, democracy, solidarity

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Learn, discuss, and play in this game about equality.

In "Equal Grounds", you and your teammates explore terms related to equality and politics. Play in teams of up to two, roll dice to score points, and guess words on the cards within 30 seconds. Cards come in two colors, offering a variety of challenges, and tiles dictate your strategy. With its blend of gameplay and learning, the game sparks discussions about equality and fosters understanding of complex concepts.

ABOUT HILVERSUM CULTURAL GAME JAM #3

Hilversum's third CGJ ran across two weeks, combining a museum-led inspiration track with a focused production week at AUAS. Students first explored Sound & Vision's Media Museum and archive, then returned to AUAS to design and prototype board and card games that examined fairness and media culture through the lens of European values. The cohort produced nine playable prototypes and documented their process and outcomes on itch.io, supported by a structured schedule, expert feedback, and templated devlogs.

Hilversum CGJ3

Date: February 17–28, 2025

Location: Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), Amsterdam, Netherlands and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 2 weeks (pre-CGJ activities and a 1 week CGJ)

Participants: 23 students from the Creative Research Methods minor (AUAS)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (8 team games plus 1 solo game after a team split)

Theme: That's Not Fair! (Games for Culture)

THE CHANCE OF YOUR LIFE

Created by: Team The Chance of Your Life
Inspired by: 'The Propaganda Game' in the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision
Building on: Social inequalities
Find game [here](#).

Fight your way up against social inequalities.

A strategic board game for 2-4 players that explores self-development, technological progress, and societal inequality. Players embody unique characters, each with different starting advantages, as they earn Self Development Points (ZOP) by making choices and overcoming obstacles. The first to reach 800 ZOP and return to the center wins.

VIRAL SPIRAL

Created by: Tim, Floor, Beyza, Sophie
Building on: Human dignity
Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum
Find game [here](#).

Manage the chaos of misinformation as an influencer.

"Viral Spiral" is a strategy and social deduction game where players act as influencers deciding whether to share, report, or ignore news articles. With reputation at stake, players must critically assess information to avoid spreading misinformation.

CYBER CRISIS

Created by: Daan Koekkoek, Kaj-Benjamin Sitanala and Ryan Vries

Inspired by: Archive clips from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Building on: Human dignity

Find game [here](#).

A fast-paced card game where players battle a powerful Phone.

A strategic role-playing card game tackling cyberbullying and digital fairness. Players face off against a formidable Phone that wields their past online actions as weapons. Blending strategy and chance, the game explores the impact of digital interactions while reinforcing EU values like dignity and responsible communication.

Access the game

THE OTTER SIDE

Created by: Team Otterbende

Inspired by: Gamedesign in the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Building on: Empathy and environmental responsibility

Find game [here](#).

A game of otters struggling against human-made threats to find a safe habitat.

A luck-based board game where players experience the struggles of endangered European otters. Facing pollution, habitat loss, and human dangers, they must collect resources to survive. The game raises awareness of environmental protection and highlights gaps in EU policies, urging players to rethink the role of nature in governance.

Access the game

THE RACE THROUGH THE NETHERLANDS

Created by:

Building on: Equality

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

A race across the Netherlands where players use strategy to reach the finish line first.

"The Race Through the Netherlands" is a competitive board game where players travel through forests, moors, and villages, encountering obstacles and opportunities that shape their journey. With unique character abilities and strategic decision-making, players must adapt to changing conditions to win.

THE NEIGHBOURS

Created by: Team De Buren

Inspired by: Loneliness among the elderly

Building on: Human dignity

Find game [here](#).

Fight elderly loneliness through small but meaningful actions.

Brighten the lives of senior citizens through thoughtful interactions! Players earn emotional points by performing acts of kindness, such as sharing a meal, arranging visits, or fostering connections between elderly characters. By engaging with personal stories and unique needs, players develop empathy and understanding.

RIGGED RAILS

Created by: Team 4

Inspired by: Inclusion of meaningful choices

Building on: Equality and human rights

Find game [here](#).

What if we're all on the same train, but in different classes?

'Rigged Rails' is a board game about class conflict, where players race to first class on a train while facing an unfair system. Earn money through luck, work, or crime, but beware: your character's background determines how easy the journey will be.

THE SOCIAL LADDER

Created by:

Building on: Human dignity, solidarity

Inspired by: The experience in the Sound and Vision museum

Find game [here](#).

Experience social inequality through unique characters with different advantages and struggles.

A board game where players experience social inequality through unique characters with different advantages and struggles.

ABOUT HILVERSUM CULTURAL GAME JAM #4

Hilversum's fourth CGJ invited students to dive into the Netherlands' long and complicated relationship with water. Titled Heritage Remixed: Tides of Heritage, the CGJ asked participants to reinterpret archival materials, historical events, and cultural narratives about water, resilience, and community. Taking place across three very different creative sites, the CGJ mirrored its theme: movement, flow, and collaboration. Over four days, students explored how the Dutch battle against rising waters could become a story of shared values and translated into playful and meaningful experiences.

Hilversum CGJ4

Date: September 10-16, 2025

Location: Dropstuff Media (DM) Shelter, Soesterberg, Netherlands; Utrecht University of

Applied Sciences (HU), Utrecht, Netherlands; and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 4 days (spread over 2 weeks)

Participants: 28 students from Communication and Media Design (HU)

Number of Games: 7 prototypes

Theme: Heritage Remixed (Games through Culture), used archival materials to imagine the future relationship with water in the Netherlands

WET FEET

Created by: Team Mean Girls
Building on: Equality and democracy
Inspired by: Extreme weather events due to climate change
 Find game [here](#).

Do you only think of yourself, or will you help build a future where everyone stays dry and alive.

The water level is rising, and not everyone is facing the same challenges. Some live high and safe, others low and vulnerable. Yet, everyone is dependent on each other. Only through support and cooperation will the entire polder remain dry. But will you stick your neck out and help others, even if it costs you land or resources?

MEESTROMEN

Created by: Team Express
Building on: Human dignity and democracy
Inspired by: Stills from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision
 Find game [here](#).

Save your own land from flooding and/or help someone else from the same fate.

This quick boardgame will let you manage your own 'waterschap'. Will you act fast enough to prevent your waterschap from flowing over with water and will you help others save theirs? The Netherlands has a long history of the dangers of the water that surrounds the small country. Protect the country from these dangers!

GENERATION PLASTIC SOUP

Created by: Team The Riff

Building on: Equality and rule of law

Inspired by: The pictures in the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Find game [here](#).

The old vs the new generation are battling for their own agenda.

This game is about plastic polluting the ocean and how different generations are looking at this so-called 'plastic soup'. We have rights to have clean water, but tension between generations, values, and visions of the future confronts the player with difficult dilemmas. How can we find solutions where we're all treated like equals?

TERRA MATER

Created by: Team Terra Mater

Building on: Human dignity

Inspired by: Archivematerials about the Watersnoodsramp in 1953 from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Find game [here](#).

No one knows what lies ahead, but all must climb if they wish to see tomorrow.

The dams holding the water out of the mountainside broke. The water is rising at an alarming rate. Villages become unlivable, forests vanish and familiar places are disappearing. Yet life endures. Humans carry stories of their ancestors, while animals guard the memory of the wild. You must spin the wheel and reach into the bag of fate.

FLASH FLOOD

Created by: Team Flash Flood

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Dutch flood disasters

Find game [here](#).

Fields are sinking under water, and your animals are in danger!

You are a farmer in the Netherlands. Every day your animals – cows, horses, sheep and chickens – graze peacefully in the fields. Earth is getting warmer. High in the Alps, the ice and snow are melting increasingly faster. It's up to you to rescue them. Only the smartest and bravest farmer will succeed in saving the animals.

Access the game

FLIPPER FRONT

Created by: Team 3

Building on: Rule of law

Inspired by: Climate change impact

Find game [here](#).

Seals fight for survival in the North Sea.

A cooperative boardgame where seals fight for survival in a future Netherlands. Rising seas open new habitats while government, dikes, islands, and laws stand in their way. Seals try to protect the North Sea in a dystopian world where the government starts expanding into their waters.

Access the game

SMIT AND THE STORM

Created by: Team Orange

Building on: Human Dignity

Inspired by: The flooding disaster in the Netherlands in 1953

Find game [here](#).

Escape the flood before history repeats itself.

"Smit en de Storm" (Smit and the Storm) is an educational escape room based on the devastating Watersnoodramp (the North Sea flood of 1953). Using real survivor stories, we created an immersive experience that teaches what happened during the disaster and how to respond in such situations. Our prototype features a scale model of the escape room and interactive puzzles. Players follow Smit's story while experiencing the tension and choices faced during the flood. Will you escape before the waters rise? Learn from history, because it could happen again.

CULTURAL GAME JAMS ÓBIDOS

ABOUT ÓBIDOS CULTURAL GAME JAM #1

The first Óbidos CGJ (CGJ1) was held on February 6–9, 2024 in the historic town of Óbidos, Portugal. Over the course of four days, 26 young participants collaborated with facilitators, cultural experts, and game industry professionals to create nine original prototypes. Inspired by Óbidos's UNESCO designation as a City of Literature, CGJ1 sought to reflect on the role of literature and books to enrich our cultural experiences into playful, interactive experiences.

This CGJ was a four-day residential CGJ, where participants lived, shared meals, and worked together in a shared creative space. CGJ1 combined lectures, cultural visits, creative workshops, and intensive prototyping. Participants drew inspiration from the medieval setting, bookshops, libraries, and literary history of Óbidos, blending local culture with European values in their games. The event concluded with a public showcase where games were presented to peers, facilitators, and local stakeholders such as the Mayor of Óbidos, followed by a reflective roundtable.

Óbidos CGJ1

Date: February 6–9, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 26 youth (ages 18–28)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (one made by Professors from Lusófona University)

Theme: Óbidos as UNESCO City of Literature

BOOKDWELLER

Created by: David Mendes, Ricardo Louro, Daniel Fernandes, Vasco Caleiro

Building on: Cultural preservation, freedom

Inspired by: Óbidos City of Literature

Find game [here](#).

Harness ancient wisdom from lost books to battle mythic foes.

In "BookDweller" you are a powerful wizard gathering knowledge and strength from old lost books to fight ancient myths and enemies in Óbidos. Use power spells to defeat powerful bosses and seal their tales.

IN SEARCH FOR WORDS

Created by: Eduardo Rocha, Gonçalo Sampaio, Hugo Silva, Leonardo Henrique and Tomás Cardoso

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature

Building on: Cultural preservation

Find game [here](#).

Will you get through the awful writer's block? Or will you let your imagination be taken away by this greedy screenbound world?

Overcome writer's block in this magical platformer inspired by Óbidos, a historic medieval town in Portugal. Help Joaquim, a rich and famous Portuguese writer with writer's block, collect special Metal Letters, regain his lost imagination, discover the magic word, and overcome his struggle.

LITERATURE DEFENSE: GUARDIAN OF ÓBIDOS

Created by: João Rodrigues, Lee Dias
Building on: Freedom, cultural preservation
Inspired by: Óbidos City of Literature
Find game [here](#).

Protect Óbidos from invasion with magical bookstores.

In "Literature Defense: Guardian of Obidos" you must defend the Castle of Óbidos against the French invasion by building magical bookstores and transforming your surroundings through conversations with the bookseller.

LOST IN WORDS

Created by: Paula Martins, Maximiliano Blanco, Leonardo Henrique, Henrique Monteiro
Building on: Cultural preservation
Inspired by: Óbidos City of Literature
Find game [here](#).

Transform your surroundings through conversations with a magical bookseller.

Embark on an enchanting journey through the pages of the Livraria de Santiago-inspired world, where every conversation with the bookseller transforms the very fabric of your surroundings. Dive into a mesmerizing narrative experience where words have the power to shape reality.

WALLS OF COLOR

Created by: Júlia Costa, Rodrigo Marques and Sónia Raposo

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature.

Building on: Cultural preservation

Find game [here](#).

Keep Óbidos pristine by stopping tourists from defacing its walls.

Óbidos is a breathtaking town with a beautiful castle, vast brick walls, and white houses with intense blue accents. However, tourists keep painting on the walls! Your job is simple: clean and prevent tourists from rubbing blue paint on the white walls. Keep the village pristine and beautiful.

PUSS IN BOOKS

Created by: António Rodrigues, Gabriela Branco

Building on: Cultural preservation

Inspired by: Óbidos City of Literature

Find game [here](#).

Guide a cat through literary dreams inspired by an Óbidos library.

In "Puss in Books," embark on a journey guiding a cat through dreams inspired by an Óbidos library. Traverse diverse literary worlds and craft an enchanting narrative as the feline explores captivating stories within its dreams. Experience a blend of imagination and adventure, where each dream unveils new challenges and discoveries in a quest to uncover the essence of literary magic.

STORYTELLER

Created by: Paulo Silva, Daniel Costa, Ivan Emidio, Mariana Martins, João Nogueira, Dinis Ferreira and Bruno Alegria

Building on: Freedom and democracy

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature

Find game [here](#).

Replace fake books with real ones to preserve Óbidos' cultural heritage.

In 20th century Óbidos, during the Estado Novo regime, a man discovers the city walls being rebuilt with fake books by Salazar's orders. Determined to preserve literary culture, he embarks on a quest to find uncensored books and replace the fake ones, safeguarding the integrity of knowledge and freedom of expression.

TSUNDOKU

Created by: João Nogueira, Mariana Martins, Bruno Alegria, Ivan Emídio, Dinis Ferreira, Daniel Costa, Paulo Silva

Building on: cultural preservation

Inspired by: Óbidos City of Literature

Find game [here](#).

Capture magical book monsters to build the bookish wall of Óbidos.

In "Tsundoku," a humble peasant from Óbidos sets out on a mission to capture magical book monsters for the construction of the village's bookish wall. Navigate various challenges and obstacles to protect the community from these enchanted creatures. Explore a whimsical world where books take on the form of formidable foes, each requiring unique strategies to capture. Build a collection of these magical beings to fortify the village's defenses and uphold its cultural heritage.

ABOUT ÓBIDOS CULTURAL GAME JAM #2

The second CGJ in Óbidos (CGJ2) took place from April 29 to May 2, 2024, bringing together 40 young participants to design games inspired by the biodiversity of the Óbidos Lagoon. The event focused on raising awareness of sustainability and environmental stewardship by embedding the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into the design process. Pre-CGJ activities were held in March and April, including an online informational session, an expert lecture about the SDGs and biodiversity, and a guided lagoon visit led by local cultural and biodiversity experts. The participants worked intensively for four days at the Creativity square, producing 14 digital prototypes.

Óbidos CGJ2

Date: April 29 – May 2, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 40 participants (25 university students, 15 secondary school students, ages 15–25)

Number of Games: 14 prototypes

Theme: Sustainability and Biodiversity – Óbidos Lagoon, connecting to SDGs 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land)

BLOOMING SHALLOWS

Created by: David Mendes, Ricardo Louro, Daniel Fernandes and Vasco Caleiro
Building on: Sustainability
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem
Find game [here](#).

Build your village while maintaining ecological balance.

Face the task of constructing and expanding your village while maintaining a delicate balance in resource consumption to preserve the surrounding ecosystem. Strategically manage materials to foster sustainable growth and overcome environmental challenges, ensuring the prosperity and harmony of your evolving community within the serene Shallows.

BIRDIPEDIA

Created by: Luan Velho, Pedro Batista and Daniela Sousa
Building on: Life on land and below water
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem
Find game [here](#).

Preserve bird species in the Óbidos Lagoon in an unconventional manner.

Living in the Óbidos Lagoon, an old lady and her pet, Lucas, an octopus, are constantly in fear that the birds that live near them will someday disappear. So they took it upon themselves not to let it happen. By buying a bazooka that can shoot Lucas without harming him so that he can catch the birds to collect, study and preserve them.

ÓBIDOS WATCHING

Created by: António Rodrigues, Afonso Cunha, Eduardo Rocha, Gabriela Branco and Júlia Costa
Building on: Rule of law and life on land
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem
Find game [here](#).

Document new species and identify littering tourists while keeping detailed records of offenses.

Photograph new species while ensuring the protection of bird habitats by removing barking dogs. Identify and capture photo evidence of tourists littering or trespassing, meticulously recording offenses. Engage in vigilant observation and documentation to preserve the natural environment and promote responsible tourism practices in Óbidos.

OTTERWAY

Created by: José Reis, Madalena Cagido and Tiago Berlim
Building on: Rule of law, life below water
Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem
Find game [here](#).

Help the otter clean the Óbidos Lagoon while managing its survival needs.

OtterWay is a survival game where you play as an otter trying to clean the Óbidos Lagoon, however you must manage your hunger and oxygen levels. There are two types of trash: plastic/metal and glass. You must put the trash in the respective bin in order to get points. There are also fishermen trying to catch you with nets.

SALTY FROG

Building on: Life on land and below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Rescue frogs from the salty waters of Óbidos Lagoon.

Save all the frogs from the Óbidos Lagoon salty water.

SPIRIT OF THE LAKE

Created by: Gonçalo Sampaio, Leonardo Henrique, Tomás Cardoso, Hugo Silva, Inês Gomes and Eduardo Rocha

Building on: Life on land and below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon ecosystem

Find game [here](#).

Roam the Óbidos Lagoon as a fox spirit, ensuring nature's balance.

A fox was possessed by the spirit of the lake. Now, in this new body, the spirit roams around the Óbidos Lagoon to check if the animals and their habitats are according to the Nature regulations.

BIZ FLAMINGO

Created by: Tomás Franco, Eduardo Rocha, Henrique Monteiro

Building on: Óbidos Lagoon

Inspired by: Life on land and below water

Find game [here](#).

Protect the flamingos of the Lagoon from vanishing.

In "Biz Flamingo," you must safeguard the vibrant flamingo population in the Lagoon from vanishing. Uncover the reasons behind their disappearance and balance ecological harmony to ensure the survival of these majestic birds.

CRIMINAL FAUNA IDENTIFICATION

Created by: Gabriela Branco, João Nogueira, Afonso Cunha, Júlia Costa, Mariana Martins

Building on: Óbidos Lagoon

Inspired by: Rule of law, life on land

Find game [here](#).

Investigate your suspects and find the guilty bird.

In "Criminal Fauna Identification," assume the role of a detective investigating mysterious cases involving suspect birds. Each case file presents a unique scenario where you analyze profiles to deduce and identify the culprit. Exercise your detective skills to uncover clues and make informed judgments in this intriguing pursuit of justice.

ENCYCLOFISHIA

Building on: Life below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Help an old man fish in Lagoa de Óbidos and document species to teach his grandson about the local fauna.

In "Encyclofishia," join an old man fishing in Lagoa de Óbidos as he documents various fish species for his grandson's education. As he reels in each fish, he meticulously records information in his diary to create an encyclopedia of the lagoon's fauna. Explore the tranquil waters, uncover diverse fish species, and contribute to a legacy of knowledge passed down through generations. Enjoy the peaceful beauty of Lagoa de Óbidos while enriching your understanding of its aquatic ecosystem.

FIND!

Building on: Life on land and below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Rescue otters before they catch endangered fish in this 3D adventure.

In "FIND!," you assume the role of Matraquilho, a dedicated river keeper tasked with rescuing six otters before they deplete endangered fish populations. Navigate through a dynamic 3D environment, using strategy and quick reflexes to locate and safeguard the otters. Each successful rescue brings you closer to unlocking a chest containing a coveted final reward. Immerse yourself in this adventure, where conservation meets action in a race against time to preserve the delicate balance of the river ecosystem.

FISHING SIMULATOR

Building on: Life below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Catch various fish species in Lagoa de Óbidos for the local restaurant.

In "Fishing Simulator," you embark on a third-person fishing adventure set in the serene Lagoa de Óbidos. Your mission is to catch various fish species inhabiting the lagoon to supply the local restaurant. Master fishing techniques, adapt to environmental conditions, and optimize your catches for profitability. Enjoy the tranquil beauty of Óbidos Lagoon while contributing to the culinary delights of the community with your fresh catches.

MOUSE HUNTER

Building on: Life on land

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Exterminate rats on Mouse Island for Queen Dona Maria I of Portugal.

In "Mouse Hunter," assume the role of a hunter dispatched by Queen Dona Maria I of Portugal to eradicate a rat infestation on Mouse Island within the Óbidos Lagoon. Navigate the island's terrain, strategically employing traps and tactics to eliminate the vermin menace threatening local ecosystems. Fulfill your royal mandate with skill and efficiency to restore harmony to the island under royal decree.

THE CROSSING OF THE ÓBIDOS LAGOON

Created by:

Building on: Life on land and below water

Inspired by: Óbidos Lagoon

Find game [here](#).

Study and capture seagulls in the Óbidos Lagoon to understand their population.

In "Travessia Aquática Da Lagoa de Óbidos", you are an ecologist working on the Óbidos Lagoon studying the seagull population and have to capture some specimens.

THE UNFOLDING OF AN ADDICTION

Created by:

Building on: Óbidos Lagoon

Inspired by: Life below water

Find game [here](#).

Fish for the Queen and learn about each species, fueling a passion for fishing.

In "The unfolding of an addiction", Manel fishes for the Queen, providing information on each catch. Manel gains a love for fishing as he feeds the Queen's addiction.

ABOUT ÓBIDOS CULTURAL GAME JAM #3

The third Óbidos CGJ took place on February 4–7, 2025, marking the cultural hub’s contribution to the glocal “That’s Not Fair!” theme. Over four days, 38 youth participants designed nine prototypes inspired by Portugal’s democratic history, linking the clandestine 1973 “Reunion of the Captains” in Óbidos with the 1974 April 25th Carnation Revolution. The CGJ balanced cultural exploration with creative game-making, encouraging participants to reflect on values of freedom, justice, and democracy in playful, critical ways.

Óbidos CGJ3

Date: February 4–7, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 38 youth (19 students from LU, 19 secondary school students)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (1 physical game + 8 digital games)

Theme: That’s Not Fair! (Games for Culture), Linking the theme to the December 1st “Reunion of the Captains” in Óbidos to the Portuguese April 25th Carnation Revolution

BLUE BRIGADE

Created by: Daniel Fernandes, Gabriela Branco, Lorena Bueno, Tomás Franco, António Rodrigues, Tiago Lourenço

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

Enforce state rules as a Portuguese officer before 1974. Censor civilians and uphold patriotism.

"Blue Brigade" is a satirical game where you step into the shoes of a Portuguese officer before 1974, enforcing censorship and state rules. Following orders, you block anything deemed unpatriotic, from books to casual conversations. The game's lighthearted visuals mask a deeper message about the absurdity of oppression. No matter how strict you are, revolution is inevitable.

BUFO CATCHER

Created by: Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Júlia Costa, Tiago Lourenço

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

Trust is fragile: spot the traitor before it's too late.

As the guard of a crucial revolutionary meeting, your job is to verify each guest's credentials and uncover any impostors. Cross-check IDs, analyze documents, and question attendees to ensure no infiltrators threaten the cause. Every choice matters, and the revolution depends on your vigilance. Will you spot the traitor in time, or will history take a different turn?

PATH TO FREEDOM

Created by: Henrique Ramos, Fábio Alves, Daniel Paiva, Bruno Vieira, Leonardo Tavares, Seth Vitorino

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

A single choice can change the course of history.

In "Caminho Para a Liberdade", you play as a soldier on your way home when an unexpected encounter changes everything. Approached by another soldier, you are invited to a secret meeting against the Estado Novo regime. Will you join the resistance and fight for freedom, or stay in the shadows? Your choices will shape the path to liberation.

THE CLUELESS OTÁVIO PINTO

Created by: Ana Laura Ferreira, Inês Gomes, Madalena Farinha, Paula Martins, Pedro Gouveia, Tiago Lourenço

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

One clueless man, one historic moment.

Step into the shoes of Otávio Pinto in a lighthearted parody set in Casa da Música, Óbidos. As you gather seemingly ordinary items, you unknowingly become part of a historic movement: the Carnation Revolution. Through playful exploration, uncover the hidden significance of small actions in shaping history. A satirical take on freedom and democracy, this game invites players to reflect on the power of collective change.

DIA ANTERIOR

Created by: Pavlo, Alex

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

**Every choice shapes the revolution:
will you stand and fight?**

In "Dia Anterior", step into the shoes of a university student caught in the fight against dictatorship in Portugal. Your choices shape not only your future but also the course of democracy. Navigate tense encounters, make difficult decisions, and experience the weight of responsibility. This game highlights the power of collective action and the role of individuals in shaping history. Will you take a stand or stay silent?

MESSAGE OF THE RED CLOVES

Created by: Ian Prast, Kauan Santos, Mara Frota, Ana Costa, Tiago Patrício

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

**Pass the message, evade the oppressors:
freedom depends on you.**

In "Message of the Red Cloves", players take on the role of resistance members passing secret messages while evading PIDE agents. Inspired by real historical movements, the game highlights themes of solidarity, trust, and strategic thinking. Every action matters as players work together to outmaneuver oppression. Experience the tension, triumph, and unity of a revolution in motion. Will your message reach its destination?

OPERATION ÓBIDOS

Created by: André Pereira, Rafael Saramago, Rodrigo Fonseca, Sofia Abreu
Building on: Democracy, freedom
Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution
Find game [here](#).

Lead the revolution. Every move counts!

In "Operação Óbidos", step into the role of an MFA captain in 1973, navigating the dangers of a dictatorship on the brink of change. Attend a secret meeting, recruit allies, and make critical decisions while evading PIDE surveillance. Every choice shapes the fate of the revolution—will you lead Portugal to freedom or watch the resistance crumble?

THE THREE LITTLE PIGS AND THE REVOLUTION

Created by: Amauri Oliveira, David Lourenço, Simão Bernardino
Building on: Democracy, freedom
Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution
Find game [here](#).

Three little pigs, one big revolution!

In "Os 3 Porquinhos e a Revolução", help Mamã Porquinho gain time to plan the Carnation Revolution while protecting yourself from danger. This playful take on the classic tale introduces children to the values of freedom and democracy in an engaging way. Designed to entertain while educating, the game brings history to life through fun and strategy. Will you outsmart the threats and help make history?

SOMBRAS DO REGIME

Created by: Leonardo, Diogo, Bernardo, João

Building on: Democracy, freedom

Inspired by: Portugal's Carnation Revolution

Find game [here](#).

Uncover the truth, or be silenced.

In "Sombras do Regime", you play João, a young journalist in 1974 Portugal, fighting against censorship and oppression. Caught in a web of secrets and danger, every decision shapes his fate. Will he expose the truth and aid the revolution, or fall victim to the regime's control? Your choices determine the outcome in this tense, narrative-driven experience.

ABOUT ÓBIDOS CULTURAL GAME JAM #4

The fourth Óbidos CGJ, held on May 13–16, 2025, invited secondary school and university students to reinterpret local folklore and cultural traditions through game making. Hosted again in the medieval town of Óbidos, the jam combined artistic exploration with collaborative learning, encouraging participants to remix heritage narratives into playable forms. The event followed the EPIC-WE framework, with an emphasis on freedom as the guiding European value. Participants transformed myths, local legends, and cultural imagery into interactive experiences that reflected contemporary issues of identity, belonging, and creativity.

Óbidos CGJ4

Date: May 13–16, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 41 total (20 from Escola Secundária Josefa de Óbidos; 21 from Lusófona University)

Number of Games: 10 prototypes (one made by a teacher)

Theme: Heritage Remixed (Games through Culture), focus on local folklore heritage

MUSARFY

Created by: Arthur Santos, Inês Gomes, Lourenço Rosário, Paula Martins, Rafael Canhoto, Sabrina Silva

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Óbidos legends

Find game [here](#).

Shapeshifting rats, frightened fishermen, and a quiet fight for freedom.

"Musarfy" is a 2D top-down stealth adventure inspired by the Óbidos legend "Homens Musaranhos" (shrews men). Play as a shapeshifting rat exploring the village, gathering your tribe while avoiding fearful fishermen who hunt you. Use whistling to distract enemies and transform into human form to trick them. Experience prejudice from the hunted's perspective in this tale of acceptance.

THE SHREWS

Created by: Henrique Ramos, Bruno Vieira, Daniel Paiva, Leonardo Tavares, Seth Vitorino

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Óbidos legends

Find game [here](#).

Seek the truth beneath the waters, but some family secrets were meant to stay buried.

The Shrews / "Os Musaranhos" is a 2D adventure game inspired by the Óbidos Lagoon legend. Play as a young fisherman searching for his mysteriously disappeared grandfather through a dark forest, haunted village, and underground cave. Complete quests, gather clues, and face the shapeshifting "musaranhos" (shrews). The final boss reveals a family secret that challenges memory and sacrifice.

THE INFESTATION

Created by: Leonardo Pimenta, David Lourenço, Joao Conceição, Bernardo Constantino, Simão Bernardino, Diogo Filipe
Building on: Freedom
Inspired by: Óbidos legends

Find game [here](#).

Defend your territory from the growing plague threatening the ecosystem.

In The Infestation / "A Infestação", you play as a fisherman facing a dangerous "musaranho" (shrews) infestation threatening the ecosystem balance. Armed with a shotgun and constantly moving, run, fight, and protect your territory from this growing plague of different-sized creatures along the shoreline while controlling their population through combat.

THE SECRET OF THE MOORISH WOMAN AND THE BETRAYAL OF ÓBIDOS

Created by: Amauri Oliveira, André Pereira, Rafael Saramago, Rodrigo Fonseca, Sofia Abreu

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Óbidos legends

Find game [here](#).

Uncover secret passages, meet the Moorish guardian, and choose between conquest and compassion.

An action-adventure game inspired by Óbidos legends "Porta da Traição" and "Cova da Moira". Play as young squire Martim, sent by Afonso Henriques to find secret entrances to Óbidos Castle. Meet the Moorish guardian Zahara, free prisoner Salim, and make choices based on trust, justice, and courage that reflect EU values of human rights and freedom.

SHADOW OF VICTORY

Created by: Pavlo, Alex

Building on: Freedom

Inspired by: Óbidos legends

Find game [here](#).

Lead a young agile hero through a medieval castle, using stealth and strategy to outsmart guards and conquer the fortress.

A medieval stealth-strategy game set in Portugal where you control a young agile protagonist infiltrating a heavily guarded castle. Navigate using stealth mechanics, avoid detection by vigilant guards, and make strategic decisions that impact the narrative. Blend espionage, infiltration, and tactical thinking to complete dangerous missions in this historical adventure.

A CONQUISTA

Created by: Isaac Pais, Pedro Gouveia, Tiago Patrício,

Carolina Correia, Tiago Félix and Lourenço Rosário

Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Porta da Traição"

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Experience the human cost of war, freedom and trust through this classical tragedy retelling.

"A Conquista" is a narrative-focused adventure game exploring the Óbidos legend "Porta da Traição" (The Door of Betrayal). Infiltrate the Moor-occupied castle during its historical siege, build relationships with residents, and find a way to open the town's doors from inside.

MOIRA'S HEX

Created by: João Rodrigues and Lee Dias

Inspired by: Óbidos legends "Cova da Moira" and "Bicho do Vau"

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Defy the curse, snuff the lamps, reclaim your freedom, but don't let the Bicho do Vau hear you.

A stealth horror game combining Óbidos legends "Cova da Moira" and "Bicho do Vau". As a village resident cursed by the Enchanted Moira, you're trapped within Óbidos' walls. Venture beyond the boundaries to snuff out 5 oil lamps and lift the curse, while avoiding the lurking Bicho do Vau that hunts anyone who makes loud noises in the shadowy forest.

DEADMAN CRAWLING

Created by: Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Afonso Cunha, Lisa Carvalho, Júlia Costa, David Mendes and Daniel Fernandes

Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Covão dos Musaranhos"

Building on: Freedom

Find game [here](#).

Crawl through the caves and survive the Musaranho!

A 3D pixel horror game based on the Óbidos Musaranho legend. A fisherman and his group encounter a mysterious creature at a calm lake and flee to cave systems. In this cat-and-mouse dynamic, crawl through dark caves, use sound to navigate, and avoid the terrifying Musaranho while searching for an escape route back home.

HE MUST BE FED

Created by: André Leandro, António Rodrigues, Gabriela Branco, Mafalda Cavaco and Vera Nunes
Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Covão dos Musaranhos"
Building on: Freedom
Find game [here](#).

**Catch some fish. Feed the Musaranho.
Survive the night.**

A horror-suspense 3D fishing simulator based on the Óbidos Musaranho legend. As a newcomer fisherman, you must catch fish to feed the strange forest deity in exchange for village peace. Begin each day by fishing beneath shifting skies, check your progress on the scale, and place your catch on the altar at dusk. Ring the bell and await what answers from the dark.

